

Supporting Information – Article at *Acta Cirurgica Brasileira*

Article: Fluorescence spectroscopy for clinical transplantation liver grafts monitoring – possibilities offered by 408 nm excitation

José Dirceu Vollet-Filho, Juliana Ferreira-Strixino, Rodrigo Borges Correa, Vanderlei Salvador Bagnato, Orlando de Castro e Silva Júnior, Cristina Kurachi

1. Supporting information

1.1. On fluorescence and related optical techniques

Every optical technique relies on the observation that any physiological, morphological, or even biochemical changes associated to lesions will affect how light interacts with tissue – thus, the characteristics of the emitted fluorescence shall be modified as a consequence. This modification happens because biological tissue is composed of biomolecules and supporting structures which interact with light mostly by absorbing and/or scattering photons. The optical properties presented by those molecules will depend on light wavelength and tissue components, since most light-interacting molecules are sensitive to their environment and, particularly, to tissue metabolism¹⁻³.

Not only incoming light is modified by those processes. Tissue endogenous fluorescence (so-called “autofluorescence”) is also modified by both absorption and scattering that take place within the tissue prior to the outgoing light collection by photodetectors. Among the main fluorescence-emitting biomolecules (fluorophores) found in cells or tissue matrix are collagen, elastin, keratin, NADH, FADH and porphyrins¹. Pathological conditions of tissues such as inflammatory processes and metabolic, biochemical and structural changes shall produce modification on the absolute and relative number of fluorophores and other absorbers or scatterers. These changes will modify light behavior within the tissue when compared to the conditions of normal tissues.

Thus, the core aspect to be investigated is to identify key patterns in the detected optical signal which are characteristic of each clinical situation. Methods for such an approach have continuously been developed over time, particularly for oncological applications – for which early diagnosis is crucial for a positive prognosis, but it has also been extended and adapted for other fields⁴.

In 2006, our research group started to investigate, for the first time, a monitoring method for liver grafts transplantation based on fluorescence spectroscopy⁵. By that time, investigation was performed on fluorescence obtained by 532 nm excitation. The choice for a specific wavelength is made based on two main characteristics: its ability to produce fluorescence from the biomolecules of the tissue in question, and its ability to penetrate tissue, considered light scattering and absorption at that wavelength – since the light generating fluorescence must reach as much tissue layers as possible to provide tissue-representative

information, and the fluorescence light generated must reach the tissue surface to be collected and analyzed. At 532 nm, light penetrates further in tissue than shorter wavelengths because it is generally less absorbed and scattered by tissue molecules, although it still can produce enough fluorescence for investigation. That first study showed that it was possible to correlate fluorescence characteristics such as relative fluorescence intensity and changes in the shape of the spectral emission bands to the quality of the preservation solution perfusion and the blood reperfusion in liver grafts.

1.2. On the results not shown within the manuscript

In this supporting information document, we provide the data which was not shown within the manuscript: in Figure 1-SI(A) and Figure 1-SI(B), all the results for the analysis concerning the surviving patients 30 days post-surgery which were not shown within the article are provided. Similarly, in Figure 2-SI, all the results for the analysis concerning the deceased patients 30 days post-surgery which were not shown within the article are provided. These figures shall contribute to the reader's understanding on the discussion provided in the manuscript.

1.3. On patterns observed in surviving vs. non-surviving patients

One of the aims of this study was to provide an approach that could indicate any failure in the procedure prior to implanting a graft. However, identifying parameters that would allow for *a priori* classification of expected procedure outcomes by fluorescence is not promptly achieved. Given the large variability of spectra from patient to patient, for only two of the transplantation stages (BT and WR5) a pattern was observed on the fluorescence of surviving patients that would not reproduce for deceased patient, as shown in Figure 3-SI).

On the comparison made in Figure 3-SI, only wavelengths with variation considered expressive when compared to the others were plotted, in addition to AF stage, plotted for reference. RBEM for 507/556 nm is the one which shows the changes noticed in the process.

It could be expected that RBEM 507/556 is the ratio that shows the largest emission of fluorescence in liver for 408-nm excitation, especially due to the large presence of molecules such as collagen and elastin in liver tissue (vide Figure 2 and Croce et al.⁶), so that this RBEM becomes more sensitive to biochemical changes taking place in the tissue.

The AF stage also showed a noticeable variation for the ratio between 605 and 556 nm among patients when compared to other ratios. However, this variation was not considered a deviation from a "normality pattern", as except for one patient the ratio was very similar for all patients. For BT stage, the

physical and chemical changes induced in the graft reach their maxima both concerning the homogeneity of the preservation solution distribution within the liver and the maximum time of cold ischemia. Consequently, the largest alterations of the transplanted grafts were observed for deceased patients in BT stage, particularly for RBEM 507/556 nm.

It is noteworthy that when there is a broader range of “normality” (which was considered as the average results observed for surviving patients), WR5 stage also showed variations for the same RBEM in the same patients. Stage WR5 is the stage for which any alterations originated from the metabolic stress (that is provoked by the intense oxidative stress associated to the warm reperfusion) take place, since fluorescence collection is performed 5 min after the end of the main anastomoses.

Since we observed alterations for the same non-surviving patients at BT stage, our results provide evidence that there were complications concerning the reestablishment of blood flow during reperfusion, which may have been caused by either inefficient preservation, by a previous, unidentified problem with the donor’s organ graft, or by damage caused by necrosis or similar harm to the liver microvasculature.

1.4. On the correlation with biochemical data

In spite of the volume of information provided, it was not possible to establish a direct correlation between the several aspects assessed by blood biochemistry and fluorescence. However, among the parameters assessed, only relative variation of lactate (Lac) and prothrombin (INR) before and after procedures seemed to show a correlation with the survival status of patients^{15,16}. An expressive and simultaneous variation in the relative levels of both parameters was evident for most cases of deceased patients, in contrast to surviving patients.

A comparison between collected biochemical data and fluorescence data shows that patients that diverge from the average in biochemistry are different from those that diverge concerning fluorescence. Such a divergence between biochemical tests and fluorescence may result from the fact that fluorescence spectroscopy gives information upon tissue optical changes instead of upon biochemical metabolites’ concentration. Further, the technique collects the overall emission of every molecule irradiated (which includes several similarly emitting molecules and interaction between light emitted from them and other molecules), producing thus macroscopic information instead of information on specific concentration of molecules. In addition to this, not all molecules assessed by biochemical tests do fluoresce, thus changes in tissue regarding the concentration or characteristics of those molecules may not necessarily be reflected on optical changes such as fluorescence emission.

Therefore, however it might be possible to achieve a correlation if, e.g., the emission of specific molecules among them in tissue greatly increased or

decreased compared to that of other molecules during transplantation, this does not necessarily happen. Changes may be related to other molecules which are not under assessment on biochemical tests. From that, a correlation between the concentration values obtained from biochemical tests and fluorescence changes can be difficult to establish. This is the most probable cause for a direct correlation between biochemistry and fluorescence not to be achieved in this study.

1.5. On fluorescence collection

The prototype is composed of a 408 nm excitation laser (diode laser, 5 mW output power, avoiding any thermal reaction/damage to tissue), a spectrometer (range 350-850 nm, model USB2000, Ocean Optics®), a laptop including the LightView® acquisition software (designed for Ocean Optics® spectrometer) and a “Y-type” optical fiber (600- μ m optical core, Ocean Optics®). This probe has two optical fiber juxtaposed alongside each other. One of the fibers delivers light from a laser to target tissue (by perpendicular positioning onto tissue surface for light coupling), and the other collects light emitted from tissue delivering to the spectrometer. The spectrometer/laptop interface generates a graph of relative intensity of fluorescence as a function of wavelength. To avoid probe damaging, cross-contamination during graft assessment and interference with data, a sterile and flexible Tegaderm® film was placed between probe tip and liver surface.

In addition, typical fluorescence spectra obtained from liver for 408 nm excitation at different and representative conditions of the transplantation procedure are shown in Figure 4-SI.

References of Supporting Information (may repeat references on the article)

1. Vishwanath K, Ramanujam N. Fluorescence Spectroscopy In Vivo. In: *Encyclopedia of Analytical Chemistry*. ; 2011. doi:10.1002/9780470027318.a0102.pub2
2. Georgakoudi I, Feld MS, Muller MG. Intrinsic fluorescence spectroscopy of biological tissue. In: *Handbook of Medical Fluorescence*. Marcel Dek. New York; 2003:109-142.
3. DaCosta RS, Andersson H, Wilson BC. Molecular Fluorescence Excitation–Emission Matrices Relevant to Tissue Spectroscopy¶. *Photochem Photobiol*. 2004;78(4):384. doi:10.1562/0031-8655(2003)078<0384:mfemrt>2.0.co;2
4. Cheong WF, Prahl SA, Welch AJ. A Review of the Optical Properties of Biological Tissues. *IEEE J Quantum Electron*. 1990;26(12):2166-2185. doi:10.1109/3.64354
5. Castro-e-Silva O, Sankarankutty AK, Correa RB, et al. Autofluorescence Spectroscopy in Liver Transplantation: Preliminary Results From a Pilot Clinical Study. *Transplant Proc*. 2008;40(3). doi:10.1016/j.transproceed.2008.03.005
6. Croce AC, Bottiroli G. Autofluorescence spectroscopy and imaging: a tool for biomedical research and diagnosis. *Eur J Histochem*. 2014;58(4). doi:10.4081/ejh.2014.2461

Supporting Information Figures

Figure 1-SI(A): Ratio between emission maxima (RBEM) for wavelengths 442, 507, 556, 605 and 685 nm (patients P01, P02, P03 and P06; one graph per patient). AF = endogenous fluorescence, BT = back-table, WR60 = 60 min after warm reperfusion. Error bars represent standard deviation of measurements among the three main liver lobes. Lines connecting dots are visual guides only. The rightmost dot in each graph represents the average (with standard deviation) among different RBEM for each transplantation stage presented, so that deviation represents divergence among ratios for a same stage. "SURVIVOR" label means that a patient survived the first 30 days post-transplantation.

Figure 1-SI(B): Ratio between emission maxima (RBEM) for wavelengths 442, 507, 556, 605 and 685 nm (patients P10, P13, P14 and P15; one graph per patient). AF = endogenous fluorescence, BT = back-table, WR60 = 60 min after warm reperfusion. Error bars represent standard deviation of measurements among the three main liver lobes. Lines connecting dots are visual guides only. The rightmost dot in each graph represents the average (with standard deviation) among different RBEM for each transplantation stage presented, so that deviation represents divergence among ratios for a same stage. "SURVIVOR" label means that a patient survived the first 30 days post-transplantation.

Figure 2-SI: Ratio between emission maxima (RBEM) for wavelengths 442, 507, 556, 605 and 685 nm (patients P10, P13, P14 and P15; one graph per patient). AF = endogenous fluorescence, BT = back-table, WR60 = 60 min after warm reperfusion. Error bars represent standard deviation of measurements among the three main liver lobes. Lines connecting dots are visual guides only. The rightmost dot in each graph represents the average (with standard deviation) among different RBEM for each transplantation stage presented, so that deviation represents divergence among ratios for a same stage. “DECEASED” label means that a patient has not survived the first 30 days post-transplantation.

Figure 3-SI: The varying RBEM among surviving patients (left side in each graph) and deceased patients (right side in each graph). For AF (left graph), ratio values lie within a range of 0-15 except for one patient. For BT (central graph) and WR5 (right graph), changes take place at RBEM 507/556 for surviving patients. Codes at "x" axis represent patients, being P01, P02, P03, , P05, P06, P10, P13, P14, and P15 survivors, and P04, P07, P08, P09, P11, and P12 non-survivors.

Figure 4-SI: Typical fluorescence spectra at 408 nm excitation. Typical fluorescence spectra (408 nm excitation) for patient “P01” collected at pre-recovering stages of the transplantation: AF (autofluorescence or endogenous fluorescence, **Figure 4A-SI**), when the graft is considered completely viable and remains functional, still in the donor’s body; and BT (back-table; **Figure 4B-SI**), when the graft has gone through at least 2-3 hours under hypothermal hypoxic preservation. In all cases, spectra were collected randomly on the liver lobe’s surface for each stage.